

Biomarker Analytical Laboratories

RECETOX, Faculty of Science, Masaryk University, Czech Republic

Title: SOP to build a high-resolution mass spectral library of authentic standards acquired by LC-[ESI]-Orbitrap Fusion Tribrid mass spectrometer: Chemical exposure agents.

Date: 2025-09-01

Version: version 2

Authors: Štěpán Koudelka

Checked: Elliott Price

Summary

SOP describes building of HR-[ESI+]-MS and HR-[ESI-]-MS libraries upon authentic standards preparation, acquisition by UHPLC (Nexera X2, Shimadzu) coupled with HRMS (Orbitrap Fusion Tribrid, Thermo Fisher Scientific) and processing of acquired records (MS-Dial) followed by the features annotation (MS-Finder). SOP is the final compilation of all previously released sections, now providing complete procedure.

A) Preparation of authentic standards

Authentic pharmaceutical and pesticide standards were purchased from the Prestwick Chemical Libraries and the Restek LC Multiresidue Pesticide Standards Kit. Each aliquot containing 100 µg of standard was diluted by 66% methanol to reach the acquisition concentration of 100 ppb, i.e.: 100 ng/mL. Pharmaceuticals were acquired as individual standards while pesticides in mixes.

B) Liquid Chromatography (LC) settings of Nexera X2 with Shimadzu Instrument driver 6.5

For mobile phase A and B, UCL-SFC grade water as well as methanol (Biosolve, SARL) both including 0.1 % formic acid (Optima, LC/MS grade) were used. Separation operating in reversed phase mode was provided by pentabromobenzyl phase-based column (Cosmocore, 2.1 mm ID x 150 mm, 2.6 µm) thermostated at 45 °C with a flow rate of 0.4 mL/min. A 10 µL of standard was aspirated representing 1 ng on-column injection. Chromatography ran for 11 mins. Detailed LC setting for is shown in **Table 1**.

C) Mass Spectrometry (MS) using Orbitrap Fusion Tribrid controlled by Xcalibur 3.3 2782.34

Full scan and data-dependent acquisition (DDA) were collected at 120k and 60k resolving power with scan range of 85-1275 m/z. Tandem mass spectra were acquired by real-time collision energy (CE) optimization via HCD assisted CE for positive (10, 30, 50 %) and negative (20, 35, 50 %) electrospray ionization. Detailed MS setting is shown in **Table 2A**.

Additional settings that were used for acquisition are accessed from the Diagnostics Table in the Orbitrap Fusion Tune Application. To open it, click the **wrench icon** located at the bottom left and follow as Tools → Method → Assisted Collision Energy Settings. Detailed setting is shown in **Table 2B**.

For EASY-MAX ion source, the H-ESI sprayer was placed in the Center and 1.5 position.

D) Generation of characteristics, data processing, annotation and managing

Software

OpenBabel 3.1.1, <https://github.com/openbabel/openbabel/releases>

DataWarrior 5.2.1, <https://openmolecules.org/datawarrior/index.html>

MS-Dial 4.70, <http://prime.psc.riken.jp/compms/msdial/main.html>

MS-Finder 3.52, <http://prime.psc.riken.jp/compms/msfinder/main.html>

TXTcollector 2.0.2, <https://txtcollector.en.softonic.com/?ex=DINS-635.3>

MS-LIMA 1.54, <https://github.com/tipputa/MS-LIMA-Standard>

The **InChI** represents the most important chemical identifier to be precisely generated because the other ones are derived from this one. Process generating the other chemical identifiers must follow the order as **InChI** → **SMILES** → **InChIKey**.

Generation of InChI identifier

- 1) Use the one of the batch conversion links to generate InChI from a chemical name, CAS, CAS-RN, or the other available chemical information.
 - Chemical Translation Service: <https://cts.fiehnlab.ucdavis.edu/batch>
 - PubChem: <https://pubchem.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/>
 - CompTox Chemicals Dashboard: <https://comptox.epa.gov/dashboard/>
 - MT Service for MetaCyc: <https://metacyc.org/metabolite-translation-service.shtml>

Generate desalted, neutralized, and non-stereospecific chemical structures by OpenBabel 3.1.1

- 1) To convert InChI of chemical to SMILES use OpenBabel, follow:
 - a) For OpenBabel GUI/---- INPUT FORMAT----, select *inchi – InChI format*, tick the box *Input below (ignore input file)* and insert the previously generated InChIs to the yellow-activated space.
 - b) Below the **CONVERT** button select the following boxes:
 - Output in canonical form
 - Universal SMILES
 - Inchified SMILES
 - c) For OpenBabel GUI/---- OUTPUT FORMAT----, select *smi – SMILES format*, tick the box *Output below only (no output file)* and click the CONVERT button to generate SMILES.
- 2) To convert SMILES of chemical to SMILES w/o salt entering the library annotation, follow:
 - a) For OpenBabel GUI/---- INPUT FORMAT----, select *smi – SMILES format*, tick the box *Input below (ignore input file)* and insert the previously generated SMILES to the yellow-activated space.
 - b) Below the **CONVERT** button select the following boxes:
 - Remove all but the largest contiguous fragment
 - Do not include isotopic or chiral markings
 - c) For OpenBabel GUI/---- OUTPUT FORMAT----, select *smi – SMILES format*, tick the box *Output below only (no output file)* and click the CONVERT button to generate SMILES w/o salt.

Generate properties of chemicals by DataWarrior 5.2.1

- 1) In OSIRIS DataWarrior/File/New → Create New File/Add Column/OK → Form View/close it by cross.
- 2) Into the red-bounded Table cell with row 1 and column Text, insert SMILES w/o salt dataset → Data Form Clipboard/header descriptors and Table with *Structure of Column* and *column* including SMILES w/o salt appear.
 - Chemistry/From Chemical Structure/Add Molecular Formula/OK
 - Chemistry/From Chemical Structure/Add InChI-Key/OK
 - Chemistry/From Chemical Structure/Calculate Properties/
Monoisotopic mass of largest fragment in g/mol; most abundant isomers/OK
 - Chemistry/From Chemical Structure/Calculate Properties/
cLogP; P: conc(octanol)/conc(water)/OK
 - Chemistry/From Chemical Structure/Calculate Properties/
cLogS; S: water solubility in mol/l, pH=7.5, 25C
- 3) File/Save Special/SD-File → name the file and save as MDL SD-files (.sdf).

Compile RAW files

Compile analyte RAW files from individual RAW_profile batch folders into the combined folder without inclusion of the blank files.

Processing by MS-DIAL 4.70

1) MS-DIAL 4.70/File/New Project/Start up a project:

- a) Project file path: Browse: the combined folder
- b) Enter parameters within the bookmarks.
 - Ionization type: Soft Ionization (LC/MS, LC/MS/MS, or precursor-oriented GC/MS/MS)
 - Separation type: Chromatography (GC, LC, CE, or SFC)
 - MS method type: Conventional LC/MS or data dependent MS/MS
 - Data type (MS1): Profile data
 - Data type (MS/MS): Profile data
 - Ion mode: Positive ion mode or Negative ion mode based on acquisition mode
 - Target omics: Metabolomics

Once finished, continue by Next button.

c) New project window/Analysis file paths/Browse: select and mark the analyte RAW files from the combined folder and Open. Following the table opening, check information and continue by Next button.

d) For the analysis parameter setting, set the parameters for each bookmark with advanced settings showed in **Table 3**. Once confirmed by Finish, data processing begins and lasts depending on the virtual machine performance.

To check parameters entered: MS-DIAL/Data Processing/All processing (from peak detection).

e) MS-DIAL generate files to the combined folder:

- PAI2 file (.pai2) and DCL file (.dcl) alongside with RAW file (.raw) of an individual analyte.
- MTD2 file (.mtd2) and MSP2 file (_Loaded.msp2) named by creation: yyyy_mm_dd_hh_mm_ss.
- AEF file (.EIC.aef), ARF2 files (.arf2, _DriftSpot.arf2, _PeakProperties.arf2) and DCL file (.dcl) named by alignment creation: alignmentResult_yyyy_mm_dd_hh_mm_ss.

2) MS-DIAL 4.70/File/Open project:

By opening the previously generated MTD2 file → Loading library files... Message appears. The *File navigator* loads the processed analyte files, and the *Alignment navigator* shows the appropriate alignmentResult_yyyy_mm_dd_hh_mm_ss.

- a) Double-click the analyte file opens *Peak spot viewer* (m/z range to retention time spotting graph)
- b) Find a corresponding spot using a precursor accurate mass:
 - i) For [M+H]⁺ and [M-H]⁻ precursor adducts, i.e.: the mass of the H must be previously added or subtracted from the monoisotopic mass of a precursor
 - ii) Check the precursor isomers which usually have the same accurate mass but differ in RT
 - iii) In *Peak spot navigator*, tick the box *MS2 acquired* to select the MS2 filtering
- c) Click the spot: Search formula and structure/Go to MS-Finder program/Deconvoluted and it opens MS-FINDER 3.52 for further annotation.

Annotate by MS-FINDER 3.52

Prior to every annotation, open the Setting → Parameter setting → Analysis parameter setting section, set the parameters for each bookmark (Method, Basic, Formula finder, Structure Finder, Data Source, Retention Time, CCS) showed in **Table 4** and Save it every time before using the software.

- 1) The *File navigator* section includes analyte file named by the creation date & time, scan number, RT & precursor m/z.
- 2) By clicking the analyte file, the *File information* boxes are filled in automatically, then check and modify:
 - Name: Unknown, rewrite by the analyte name
 - Scan number, Retention time (min) & CCS (\AA^2): filled in automatically
 - Precursor m/z, Precursor type, Ion mode, Spectrum type & Collision energy (CE): check the m/z, select the adduct type of $[M+H]^+$ or $[M-H]^-$, select the ionization mode of Positive or Negative, use the Centroid one & check the CE
 - Additionally, the MS graphs show MS1 & MS/MS spectrum
- 3) By double-clicking the analyte file, the *Molecular formula finder* searches the most related analytes showing Formula, Error mDa, Error ppm, Score & Resource.
- 4) Once the compound selected, fill the previously generated chemical identifiers from DataWarrior to *File information* for
 - Formula, SMILES, InChIKey & Comment
- 5) In the *Molecular formula finder*, click the Formula/Search the structures → *Structure finder* reveals the chemical compound matched alongside with Spectrum, Structure & Meta data information
- 6) For a single fragment annotation use, Analysis/Fragment Annotation (single) → Peak assignment setting, check, and Finish.
- 7) For a stepwise fragment annotations use, Analysis/Fragment Annotation (batch job), use following the annotation of 10 analytes generated by “MS-DIAL 4.70/File/Open project” & “MS-FINDER 3.52” steps.
 - For each annotated analyte, it saves appropriate folder including SDF file (.sdf), FDT file (.fgt) and MAT shortcut to the MSDIAL_TEMP folder.
 - Export/Export peak annotation as MSP formation → From a practical point of view, save every ten annotated analytes into a single MSP file, i.e.: MSP1 for analytes 1-10, MSP2 for analytes 11-20, etc.

Merge individual MSPs to a single MSP file by TXTcollector 2.0.2

- 1) Open TXTcollector and click [Extensions and Separator](#) link to manage opening of the files.
 - extensions.txt
→ to operate msp files, type msp to the current extensions list (txt, bat, cfg, . . .) and save
 - separators.txt
→ you can add a new separator style to distinguish content of the merged files and save
- 2) Select the msp format (in the folder line), tick Include Subfolders button and open **1. Browse Folders** button to select folder including MSP files to be merged.
 - No Separator & No Filenames: optional boxes to be ticked
- 3) Click **2. Combine all files** button and after the merging, save a proper named file with corresponding extension which is usually txt.
 - For the merged file, rewrite .txt by .msp extension.

Check the annotated files by MS-LIMA 1.54

Prior to every checking, open the setting section → Setting Window → Parameter setting, and set the parameters in the **Table 5** and Save it every time before using the software.

- 1) Following the MS-LIMA opening, continue File/Import/Import (without auto saving), select and open the MSP file to be inspected.
- 2) Check the sections of Compound Identification, Spectra, MS/MS viewer and Peak Information.
- 3) Viewer/Show meta data of all spectra → *Meta information of all spectra* & the column headers.
 - By clicking the column header, the column sorting enables inspection of the annotated compound analytes. For any observed discrepancies, reannotate accordingly.

ANNEX

Table 1 Shimadzu LC Method Parameters via Shimadzu Instrument driver 6.5

Pumps	Value
Pumping Mode	Binary Flow
Total Flow (mL/min)	0.4000
Pump B Conc. (%)	35.0
B Curve	0
Pressure Range, Pump A/B, (bar)	50 – 500
Compressibility, Pump A/B	Off
Time Program	
0.01 – System Controller	Start
0.01 – Pumps – Pump B Conc. (%), Total Flow (mL/min)	35, 0.40
0.50 – Pumps – Pump B Conc. (%)	35
5.50 – Pumps – Pump B Conc. (%)	70
6.50 – Pumps – Pump B Conc. (%), Total Flow (mL/min)	98, 0.40
7.00 – Pumps – Total Flow (mL/min)	0.50
9.00 – Pumps – Pump B Conc. (%), Total Flow (mL/min)	98. 0.50
9.10 – Pumps – Pump B Conc. (%)	35
9.50 – Pumps – Total Flow (mL/min)	0.40
10.99 – Pumps – Pump B Conc. (%), Total Flow (mL/min)	35, 0.40
11.00 – System Controller	Stop
Autosampler	
Rinsing Volume (µL)	500
Rinsing Speed (µL/sec)	35
Rinse Mode	Before and After aspiration
Cooler Temperature (°C)	10
Sampling speed (µL/sec)	5.0
Sample Volume (µL)	10.0
Oven	
Temperature Control (°C)	45

Table 2A Positive and Negative Mode Settings of Orbitrap Fusion Tribid by Xcalibur 3.3 2782.34

Method Settings	Value
Application Mode	Small Molecule
Method Duration (min)	11
Global Parameters: MS Global Settings	
Infusion Mode	Liquid Chromatography
Expected LC Peak Width (s)	7
Default Charge State	1
Enable Xcalibur AcquireX method modifications	False
Internal Mass Calibration	Off
Global Parameters: Ion Source	
Ion Source Type	H-ESI
Spray Voltage	Static
Positive/Negative Ion (V)	3500/3000
Sheath Gas (Arb), mode: positive/negative	35/40
Aux Gas (Arb), mode: positive/negative	12.5/20
Sweep Gas (Arb)	0.5
Ion Transfer Tube Temp (°C)	300
Vaporizer Temp (°C)	350
APPI Lamp	Not in Use
Use Ion Source Setting from Tune	False
FAIMS Mode	Not Installed
Global Parameters: Divert Valve A	
Time (min)/Position	0/1-2
Time (min)/Position	11/1-6
Experiment#1 [MS]: Master Scan: MS OT	
Detector Type	Orbitrap
Orbitrap Resolution	120 000
Mass range	Normal
Use Quadrupole Isolation	True
Scan Range (m/z)	85-1275
RF Lens (%)	45
AGC Target (%)	Custom
Normalized AGC Target (%)	125
Maximum Injection Time Mode	Custom
Maximum Injection Time (ms)	100
Microscans	1
Data Type	Profile
Polarity	Positive/Negative
Source Fragmentation	Disabled
Scan Description	-----
Experiment#1 [MS]: Filters: Intensity	
Filter Type	Intensity Threshold

Intensity Threshold	2.50E+04
Experiment#1 [MS]: Filters: Dynamic Exclusion	
Use Common Settings	False
Exclude After n Times	3
If Occurs Within (s)	1
Exclusion Duration (s)	4
Mass Tolerance	ppm
Low	5
High	5
Exclude Isotopes	False
Perform dependent scan on a single charge state per precursor only	False
Experiment#1 [MS]: Filters: Apex Detection	
Expected Peak Width (FWHM, s)	3
Desired Apex Window (%)	65
Experiment#1 [MS]: Filters: Targeted Mass Exclusion: Mass List *	
Include Start/End Times	True
Include Intensity Threshold	False
Mass List Type	m/z
Exclusion Mass Width	ppm
Low	5
High	5
Experiment#1 [MS]: Filters: Data Dependent	
Data Dependent Mode	Cycle Time
Time Between Master Scans (s)	0.6
Experiment#1 [MS]: Scan Event Type 1: Scan: ddMS² OT HCD	
Isolation Mode	Quadrupole
Isolation Window (m/z)	0.8
Isolation Offset	Off
Activation type	HCD
HCD Collision Energy Type	Normalized
Collision Energy Mode	Assisted
HCD Assisted Collision Energies (%), mode: positive/negative	10, 30, 50/20, 35, 50
Detector Type	Orbitrap
Orbitrap resolution	60 000
Mass Range	Normal
Scan Range Mode	Define m/z range
Scan Range (m/z)	85-1275
AGC Target	Custom
Normalized AGC Target	125
Maximum Injection Time Mode	Custom
Maximum Injection Time (ms)	50
Microscans	1
Data Type	Profile

Use EASY-IC™ False

Scan Description -----

* For the parameter Filters/Targeted Mass Exclusion/Mass List, the targeted mass exclusion (TME) lists were provided by CSV format for positive (TME_List_positive.csv) and negative (TME_List_negative.csv) electrospray ionization of six blanks containing 66% methanol acquired under the same conditions as standards.

Table 2B Assisted Collision Energy Settings

Parameter Name	Parameter Value
CID Remaining Precursor Threshold (%)	20
HCD Remaining Precursor Threshold (%)	20
Evaluation Ion Trap Scan AGC Target	5000
Display Evaluation Ion Trap Scans	0

Table 3 Parameter to process the acquired RAW files by MS-DIAL 4.70

Data collection	Positive acquisition	Negative acquisition
Mass accuracy (centroid parameter)		
MS 1 tolerance (Da)	0.003	0.003
MS 2 tolerance (Da)	0.003	0.003
Data collection parameters		
Retention time begin (min)	0	0
Retention time end (min)	100	100
MS1 mass range begin (Da)	85	85
MS1 mass range end (Da)	1 275	1 275
MS/MS mass range begin (Da)	85	85
MS/MS mass range end (Da)	1 275	1 275
Isotope recognition		
Maximum charged number	2	2
Consider Cl and Br elements	True	True
Multithreading		
Number of threads	16	16
Execute retention time corrections		
	False	False
Peak Detection		
Peak detection parameters		
Minimum peak height (amplitude)	10 000	1 000
Mass slice width (Da)	0.01	0.01
Smoothing method	LinearWeighedMovingAverage	LinearWeighedMovingAverage
Smoothing level (scan)	3	3
Minimum peak width (scan)	8	8
Exclusion mass list	False	False
MS2Dec		
Deconvolution parameters		
Sigma window value	0.3	0.3
MS/MS abundance cut off (amplitude)	10	10
Exclude after precursor ion	True	True
Keep the isotopic ions until (Da)	0.5	0.5
Keep the isotopic ions w/o MS2Dec	True	True
Identification *		
MSP file and MS/MS identification setting		
Retention time tolerance (min)	1 000	1 000
Accurate mass tolerance (MS1, Da)	0.003	0.003
Accurate mass tolerance (MS2, Da)	0.003	0.003
Identification score cut off (%)	70	70
Use retention time scoring	True	True
Use retention time filtering	True	True
Text file and post identification setting		
Retention time tolerance (min)	0.1	0.1

Accurate mass tolerance (Da)	0.01	0.01
Identification score cut off (%)	85	85
<i>Spectrum cut off and report option</i>		
Relative abundance cut off (%)	0	0
Only report the top list	False	False
Adduct		
Adduct ion setting	[M+H] ⁺ , included	[M-H] ⁻ , included
Alignment		
<i>Alignment parameters setting</i>		
Result name	alignmentResult_YYYY_MM_DD_	alignmentResult_YYYY_MM_DD_
Reference file	middle batch one	middle batch one
Retention time tolerance (min)	0.05	0.05
MS1 tolerance (Da)	0.003	0.003
Retention time factor	0.5	0.5
MS1 factor	0.5	0.5
Peak counter filter (%)	0	0
N% detected in at least one group (%)	0	0
Remove features based on blank information	False	False
Sample max / blank average (fold change)	Inactive	Inactive
Sample average / blank average (fold change)]	Inactive	Inactive
Keep 'reference matched' metabolite features	Inactive	Inactive
Keep 'suggested (w/o MS2)' metabolite features	Inactive	Inactive
Keep removable feature and assign the tag	Inactive	Inactive
Gap filling by compulsion	False	False
Mobility	Inactive	Inactive
Isotope tracking		
<i>Tracking of isotope labels</i>	False	False
Labelled element	Inactive	Inactive
Non-labelled reference file	Inactive	Inactive
Use target formula library	Inactive	Inactive
Set fully labelled reference file	Inactive	Inactive

* For library building, none of the parameters after this point are relevant. They are just needed to be filled in so that MS-DIAL runs.

Table 4 Parameters to annotate processed RAW files by MS-FINDER 3.52

Basic	
Mass tolerance setting	
Mass tolerance type	ppm
Mass tolerance (MS1), (\pm ppm)	5
Mass tolerance (MS2), (\pm ppm)	5
Abundance setting	
Relative abundance cut off (%)	1
Mass range setting	
Mass range max (Da)	2 000
Mass range min (Da)	70
Formula finder	
Formula calculation setting	
LEWIS and SENIOR check	True
Isotopic ratio tolerance (%)	20
Element ratio check (covering)	Extended range (99.99%)
Element probability check	True
Element selection	True: O, N, P, S, F, Cl, Br, I, Si
<i>TMS-MEOX derivative compound</i>	False
Minimum TMS count	Inactive
Minimum MEOX count	Inactive
Options	
Maximum report number (up to 100)	100
Time out (-1 means infinite), (min)	-1
Advanced settings for AIF	False

For MS-FINDER, the only settings used for library building are the Basic & Formula Finder. The values in all other sections are irrelevant.

Table 5 Data checking parameters for MS-LIMA 1.54

Parameter setting	Value
Basic settings	
MS2 tolerance (Da)	0.005
RT tolerance for difference checking (min)	5
Min. number for consensus (samples)	1
Key of compound grouping	InChI
Visualisation settings	
Number of decimal places of m/z value	5
Each spectrum height in multiple viewer (pixel)	200
Additional settings	
Interval time to auto export (milliseconds)	1000